

Equal-Life fourth wave scientific papers

Project title: Early Environmental quality and life-course mental health effects

Project Number: 874724

Project Acronym: Equal-Life

Work package 10 - Deliverable D10.12

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication date	Change
1.1		30-06-2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 874724

H2020 program	Grant agreement numbers 874724 (Equal-Life),
Project start date: Jan 1 st 2020	Duration: 66 months
Project Coördinators: Irene van Kamp (RIVM)	

WP (number and title)	WP10: Management and Dissemination
Deliverable Number	D10.12
Deliverable Title	Fourth wave scientific papers
Due date	M66
Actual date	30-06-2025
Dissemination Level	Public

Lead beneficiary	RIVM	
Responsible authors	Irene van Kamp	
E-mail / phone responsible authors	Irene van Kamp (RIVM)	+31 62 111 2691
Reviewers	All PI's	

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Table of Contents

1	Summary	4
2	Published papers.....	4
3	Papers in preparation	6
4	Other Publications	9
5	PhD Theses defended until 30.6.2025	12

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1 Summary

This report gives an overview of the published scientific papers that were published between January 1st 2024 and June 30th 2025 in the context of the Equal-Life project (*Chapter 2*) and a list of papers per work package (WP) that are in the final stages of preparation in June 2025, to be submitted in 2025 or under review (*Chapter 3*) and a list of publications aimed at the general public (*Chapter 4*) and 4) a list of PhD theses (*Chapter 5*). For the Equal-Life publication policy, we refer to D10.2. All publications will be findable at https://zenodo.org/communities/equal_life, also the publications not mentioned here.

2 Published papers

The following scientific papers were published between January 1st 2024 and June 30th 2025 in the context of the Equal-Life project:

Peer reviewed articles

1. Afonin, A. M., Piironen, A.-K., De Sousa Maciel, I., Ivanova, M., Alatalo, A., Whipp, A. M., Pulkkinen, L., Rose, R. J., Van Kamp, I., Kaprio, J., & Kanninen, K. M. (2024). Proteomic insights into mental health status: plasma markers in young adults. *Translational Psychiatry*, 14(1), 55. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41398-024-02751-z>
2. Drouard, G., Hagenbeek, F. A., Whipp, A. M., Pool, R., Hottenga, J. J., Jansen, R., Hubers, N., Afonin, A., BIOS Consortium, BBMRI-N. L. Metabolomics Consortium, Willemssen, G., De Geus, E. J. C., Ripatti, S., Pirinen, M., Kanninen, K. M., Boomsma, D. I., Van Dongen, J., & Kaprio, J. (2023). Longitudinal multi-omics study reveals common etiology underlying association between plasma proteome and BMI trajectories in adolescent and young adult twins. *BMC Medicine*, 21(1), 508. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-023-03198-7>
3. Drouard, G., Wang, Z., Heikkinen, A., Foraster, M., Julvez, J., Kanninen, K. M., Van Kamp, I., Pirinen, M., Ollikainen, M., & Kaprio, J. (2024). Lifestyle differences between co-twins are associated with decreased similarity in their internal and external exposome profiles. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 21261. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-72354-7>
4. Dzhambov, A. M., Lercher, P., & Botteldooren, D. (2024). Childhood sound disturbance and sleep problems in Alpine valleys with high levels of traffic exposures and greenspace. *Environmental Research*, 242, 117642. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2023.117642>
5. Jansen, S. N. G., Kamphorst, B. A., Mulder, B. C., Van Kamp, I., Boekhold, S., Van Den Hazel, P., & Verweij, M. F. (2024). Ethics of early detection of disease risk factors: A scoping review. *BMC Medical Ethics*, 25(1), 25. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-024-01012-4>
6. Lercher, P., Dzhambov, A. M., & Persson Waye, K. (2025). Environmental perceptions, self-regulation, and coping with noise mediate the associations between children's physical environment and sleep and mental health problems. *Environmental Research*, 264, 120414. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2024.120414>

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7. Miliias, V., Psyllidis, A., & Bozzon, A. (2024). Bridging or separating? Co-accessibility as a measure for potential place-based encounters. *Journal of Transport Geography*, vol. 121, 104027. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2024.104027>
8. Miliias, V., Teeuwen, R., Bozzon, A., & Psyllidis, A. (2024). Crowdsourcing the influence of physical features on the likely use of public open spaces. *Computational Urban Science*, 4(1), 15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43762-024-00126-0>
9. Seitz, J., & Fels, J. (2025a). Activity-based acoustic situations in primary schools: Analyzing classroom noise and listening effort. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 157(3), 1772–1783. <https://doi.org/10.1121/10.0036129>
10. Seitz, J., Loh, K., & Fels, J. (2024). Listening effort in children and adults in classroom noise. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 25200. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-76932-7>
11. Teeuwen, R., Bozzon, A., & Psyllidis, A. (2024). Children’s access to urban greenspace: a survey of factors and measures. *Cities & Health*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23748834.2024.2387931>
12. Teeuwen, R., Miliias, V., Bozzon, A., & Psyllidis, A. (2024). How well do NDVI and OpenStreetMap data capture people’s visual perceptions of urban greenspace? *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 245, 105009. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2024.105009>
13. Telkmann, K., Gudi-Mindermann, H., Bogers, R., Ahrens, J., Tönnies, J., Van Kamp, I., Vrijkotte, T., & Bolte, G. (2025). Identification of exposome clusters based on societal, social, built and natural environment – results of the ABCD cohort study. *Environment International*, 197, 109335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2025.109335>
14. Wang, Z., Drouard, G., Whipp, A. M., Heinonen-Guzejev, M., Bolte, G., & Kaprio, J. (2024). Association between trajectories of the neighborhood social exposome and mental health in late adolescence: A FinnTwin12 cohort study. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 358, 70–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2024.04.096>
15. Wang, Z., Whipp, A. M., Heinonen-Guzejev, M., Foraster, M., Júlvez, J., & Kaprio, J. (2024). The association between urban land use and depressive symptoms in young adulthood: a FinnTwin12 cohort study. *Journal of Exposure Science & Environmental Epidemiology*, 34(5), 770–779. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41370-023-00619-w>
16. Wang, Z., Whipp, A. M., Heinonen-Guzejev, M., & Kaprio, J. (2024). Age at separation, residential mobility, and depressive symptoms among twins in late adolescence and young adulthood: a FinnTwin12 cohort study. *BMC Public Health*, 24(1), 2239. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-19734-w>
17. Wang, Z., Aaltonen, S., Teeuwen, R., Miliias, V., Peuters, C., Raimbault, B., Palviainen, T., Lumpe, E., Dick, D., Salvatore, J. E., Foraster, M., Dadvand, P., Júlvez, J., Psyllidis, A., van Kamp, I., & Kaprio, J. (2025). The urban physical environment and leisure-time physical activity in early midlife: A FinnTwin12 study. *Health & Place*, 94, 103495. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthplace.2025.103495>

These papers are also added to the continuous reporting module in the EC portal.

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3 Papers in preparation

The following papers are planned some of which in the final stages of preparation in June 2025 or are currently under review.

WP1

Belke, C., Schreckenberger, D., Benz, S., Kuhlmann, J., Dzhambov, A., Lercher, P., Klätte, M., Leist, L., Vincens, N., Persson Waye, K., Jeram, S., Ristovska, G., Spiroski, I., Kanninen, K., Alatalo, A., Selander, J., Eriksson, C., Arati, A., White, K., & van Kamp, I. (n.d.). Stress as a potential mediator in the association between exposome, mental health and cognitive development in children and adolescents: A scoping review. [to be submitted]

Klätte, M. Bergström, K.; Leist, L.; & Persson Waye, K. The role of self-regulation in the effects of environmental exposures on child mental health and cognition: A systematic review

Klätte, M., Leist, L.; Schreckenberger, D.; et al. Speech-in-noise perception predicts phonological awareness and reading in school starters instructed in German language.

Klätte, M., Schreckenberger, D. In-depth studies: school studies longitudinal comparison (German sample)

Nele De Poortere, UGent, and all partners involved in in depth study (2025) Impact of exposome on early development of hearing and attention.

Angel Dzhambov, Peter Lercher (shared), et al. Reading performance of Alpine schoolchildren in relationship with exposome components - mediation analysis.

Natalia Vincens , Kerstin Persson Waye, (shared), WP1 members (2025) Scoping review the impact of exposome on mental health and cognition among children mediated by sleep. (will be delayed until September 2025).

Gordana Ristovska/Natalia Vincens, WP1 members (2025) Environmental factors and child cognitive development: a scoping review of exposome research trends.

Kerstin Persson Waye, et al. (2025) In-depth studies: An exposome perspective on sleep and mental health among adolescents.

Nele Depoortere, Partners in-depth study (2025) Exploring the Multi-Faced Impact of Early-Life Environmental Sound Exposure at Home on Primary School Children

Timothy Van Renterghem, RWTH Aachen?, partners in-depth study (2025) School noise and reverberation and cognitive development of pre-school children

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Angel Dzhambov, Peter Lercher (2025) In-depth studies: pathway of green space – stress – mental health in children

Kerstin Persson Waye/Natalia Vincens (shared) et al 2025 WP1 members. New insights into the conceptual framework for children's exposome mental health, well-being and cognition (2025).

WP2

Zhiyang Wang, Gabin Drouard, Aleksei Afonin, Núria Botella, Carmen Peuters, Aino-Kaisa Piironen, Alyce. M. Whipp, Boris Cheval, Libor Šulc, Marja Heinonen-Guzejev, Maria Foraster, John Gulliver, Jenny Selander, Payam Dadvand, Jordi Júlvez, Irene van Kamp, Katja M. Kanninen, Jaakko Kaprio, Equal-Life Scientific Team (2025) Associations between the mid-adolescent external exposome and proteomic biomarkers of mental health [under review] preprint available: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.12.18.24319208>.

Afonin, A. M., Piironen, A.-K., Julvez, J., van Kamp, I., & Kanninen, K. M. (2024). Plasma proteome demonstrates sex-specific associations with mental health risks in adolescents. [pre-print, submitted to Psychiatry Research]medRxiv. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.12.16.24319062>

Katja Kanninen (Aino-Kaisa Piironen), UEF, Walnuts cohort owners, Metabolomics identifies associations of plasma markers and altered fatty acid profiles with the risk of mental health issues in adolescents

WP3

Loh, K., Seitz, J., Nolden, S., Gudi-Mindermann, H., Dohmen, M., van Kamp, I., Botteldooren, D., Hornikx, M., Bolte, G., & Fels, J. (2025). Cognitive milestone at the age of four: Intentional switching of auditory selective attention in preschool children. [Manuscript submitted for publication]. *Scientific Reports*.

M.E.Terzakis, F. Naim, C. Van hoorickx, M.Hornikx, D.Fecht., A.L. Hansell, J. Gulliver (2025) Estimation of Outdoor-to-Indoor Noise Attenuation for Night-Time Residential Noise Exposure based on Noise Indicators. *Applied acoustics* [under review]

M.E.Terzakis, C. Van hoorickx, M.Hornikx, (2025) An outdoor-to-indoor sound propagation modelling framework for evaluating noise exposure applications. *Acta Acustica* [under review]

Arnaud Can, Goteborg team (2025) Characterizing appropriate outdoor and indoor sound environments for children mental health

Arnaud Can, Dick Botteldooren, ABCD, ALPINE (2025) on the selection on noise indicators for exposome assessment and their estimation

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Dick Botteldooren, Timothy Van Renterghem (2025) Machine Learning surrogate model for noise exposure indicators

Dick Botteldooren (2025) on the selection on indicators for exposome assessment

Seitz, J., & Fels, J. (2025b). Differences between subjective and behavioral listening effort in children across age and task complexity. [Manuscript under review]. *Ear & Hearing*.

Seitz, J., Sinarso, A., Bolte, G. & Fels, J. (2025c). Socioeconomic Status Shapes Children's Listening Effort Under Classroom Noise. [Manuscript will be submitted 07/2025]. *Journal of Environment and Behavior*.

Seitz, J., Westphal, V., & Fels, J. (2025d). Tentative: Subjective and behavioural listening effort across task difficulty in preschool children. [Manuscript in progress]. *Trends in Hearing*.

Seitz, J., Berger, J., & Fels, J. (2025e). Tentative: Subjective and behavioural listening effort across task difficulty in adults. [Manuscript in progress]. *Trends in Hearing*.

Seitz, J., Berger, J., & Fels, J. (2025f). Tentative: Comparing measures for assessing listening effort in children. [Manuscript in progress]. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*.

WP4:

Tönnies J, Ahrens J, Hasselder P, van Houten P, van Eerten JJ, White M, Weber M, Bolte G. Tackling transport poverty with offers for shared mobility – a qualitative analysis on a mobility hub in a deprived neighbourhood from a public health perspective. *Cities & Health* [revised and resubmitted]

Ahrens J, White M, Jeram S, Ristovka G, Koning J, Gudi-Mindermann H, Tönnies J, Czwikla G, Weber M, Bolte G. A framework to consider equity in urban intervention planning, implementation, and evaluation. [to be submitted]

Gabriele Bolte, Irene van Kamp, Hendriek Boshuizen (2025) Combining the physical and social exposome (theory paper). In preparation

WP6:

Hendriek Boshuizen, Irene van Kamp, Carmen Peuters, Botteldooren (2025) Characterising the exposome (method paper)

Hendriek Boshuizen, Equal-Life scientific team (2025) Pooled analysis.

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WP7:

Libor Sulc, et al. (2025) on ADHD diagnosis in children (at or before age 16) and prenatal exposome (social and physical).

Fan Wu (2025) on autism diagnosis in children (at or before age 16) and prenatal exposome (social and physical).

Karl Lundin Remnélius (2025) ADHD/autism and the differences between these diagnoses by sex.

Carmen Peuters,van Kempen, E., Jordi Julvez et al. (2025) The physical and social external exposome during early life and child selective attention: a multi-cohort study.

WP8/9:

Sandionigi, A., Benz S. et al. (2025), Simplifying Access to Mental Health Research: The Equal-Life Toolbox and Guidebook

Sandionigi, A., Benz S et al. (2025), Investigation into awareness of the effects of factors that can influence children's mental health. An exposome perspective.

WP10:

Irene van Kamp, Equal-Life scientific team (2025) Overall outcomes Equal-Life.

Irene van Kamp, Erik Lebret, Julia Hartman, Kim van Wijk (2025) Lessons learned interdisciplinary collaboration.

4 Other Publications

1. Bolte, G. (2024). Social-epidemiological perspectives on environmental health research. International EXPOHEALTH Workshop, Mainz, Germany, 30.10.2024.
2. Dohmen, M. E., Braat-Eggen, Ella, Kemperman, Astrid, & Hornikx, Maarten. (2024). A laboratory experiment exploring the effect of chronic- and background noise on cognitive performance and motivation. 30th International Congress on Sound and Vibration, Amsterdam, The Netherlands.
3. Drouard, Gabin. (2024). Multi-Omic Associations of Epigenetic Age Acceleration are Heterogeneously Shaped by Genetic and Environmental Influences. Talk at WORKSHOP W3 – New developments in twin studies of Epigenetics. The Joint 7th World Congress on Twin Pregnancy and 19th Congress of the International Society of Twin Studies (ISTS), Assisi, Perugia, Italy, September 26th – 28th, 2024.

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4. Klatte, M.; Leist, L.; Belke, C. Spilski, J.; Schreckenberger, D.; Benz, S.; Kuhlmann, J.; Haba, A. ; Lachmann, T. (2025). Sprachverständnis im Störgeräusch als Prädiktor von phonologischer Bewusstheit, Buchstabenkenntnis und Leseleistungen in der Schuleingangsphase [speech perception in noise as predictor of letter knowledge, phonological awareness and reading abilities in school starters]. Biannual Conference of the Educational Psychology Group of the German Psychological Society, Jena, 2025.
5. Leist, L., Belke, C., Kuhlmann, J., Benz, S., Haba, A., Schreckenberger, D., Spilski, J., Lachmann, T., & Klatte, M. (2024). The role of noise as part of neighborhood quality and its impact on well-being in German preschoolers: Results from the Equal-Life project. In 53rd International Congress & Exposition on Noise Control Engineering (INTER-NOISE), Nantes, France. https://doi.org/10.3397/IN_2024_3937.
6. Miliadis, V., & Psyllidis, A. (2025). CTwalk: A tool for mapping potential inter-population encounters in X-minute neighborhoods. In: Dennett, A., Cramer-Greenbaum, S., & Zhong, C. (eds.): Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Computational Urban Planning and Urban Management (CUPUM 2025), London, UK.
7. Peuters, Carmen, Botella, Núria, Dadvand, Payam, et al. (2024). The early life physical and social external exposome and child selective attention: A multi-cohort study. Barcelona Exposome Symposium.
8. Peuters, Carmen, Botella, Núria, Dadvand, Payam, et al. (2024). The physical and social exposome during early life and child selective attention: A multi-cohort study. ISEE Young Conference. Abstracts ISEE Young 2024.
9. Persson Waye, K. (2024). Keynote: A child perspective on noise exposure and health effects – Challenges and strategies. In 53rd International Congress & Exposition on Noise Control Engineering (INTER-NOISE), Nantes, France.
10. Persson Waye, K. (2025). Noise and health assessments from a child course approach. In Proceedings of Fortschritte der Akustik - DAGA 2025: 51. Jahrestagung für Akustik. Deutsche Gesellschaft für Akustik.
11. Piironen, A. K., Afonin, A., van Kamp, I., Julvez, J., Kaprio, J., Lakka, T., Tolmunen, T., & Kanninen, K. M. (2024). Susceptibility biomarkers of mental health issues in adolescence. In Proceedings Neuroscience Applied/ECNP 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nsa.2024.104270>.
12. Psyllidis, A., & Miliadis, V. (2025). Population-specific factors of pedestrian accessibility: Bridging practitioner insights and accessibility metrics. In: Dennett, A., Cramer-Greenbaum, S., & Zhong, C. (eds.): Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Computational Urban Planning and Urban Management (CUPUM 2025), London, UK.

13. Seitz, J., Berger, J., & Fels, J. (2024, September). Exploring listening effort in adults: An overlapping dual-task paradigm in multi-talker babble noise [Poster presentation]. World Congress of Audiology 2024, Paris, France.
14. Seitz, J., Loh, K., & Fels, J. (2024, March). Assessing listening effort in primary school children: A dual-task approach. In Proceedings of Fortschritte der Akustik - DAGA 2024: 50. Jahrestagung für Akustik. Deutsche Gesellschaft für Akustik.
15. Seitz, J., & Fels, J. (2025, March). A questionnaire suitable to assess listening effort in children and adults. In Proceedings of Fortschritte der Akustik - DAGA 2025: 51. Jahrestagung für Akustik. Deutsche Gesellschaft für Akustik.
16. Seitz, J., & Fels, J. (2025, May). How do classroom activities influence noise levels and students' listening effort? International Congress on Acoustics 2025, New Orleans, LA, United States.
17. Spilski, J., Jubran, O., Klätte, M., Lachmann, T., Dzhambov, A., Schreckenberger, D., Kuhlmann, J., Benz, S., Boshuizen, H., Lercher, P. (2025). The effects of road traffic noise exposure on children's well-being: Results of causal pathway analyses in the context of the exposome concept. Proceedings of Inter-Noise 2025. Sao Paulo, Brazil, 24-27 August 2025.
18. Spilski, J., Lercher, P., van Kempen, E., Giehl, C., Dzhambov, A., Klätte, M., Schreckenberger, D., & EqualLife Scientific Team. (2024). The importance of traffic noise exposure among other exposome variables on children's wellbeing: Results from three studies across three countries. In 53rd International Congress & Exposition on Noise Control Engineering (INTER-NOISE), Nantes, France. https://doi.org/10.3397/IN_2024_3964.
19. Sulc, Libor, et al. (2024). Multi-cohort study analysis of exposome and its association with ADHD phenotypes in children, oral presentation. ISEE Young Conference in Rennes, France (June 5–7, 2024). Abstracts ISEE Young 2024.
20. Telkmann, K., Gudi-Mindermann, H., Bogers, R., Ahrens, J., Tönnies, J., van Kamp, I., Vrijkotte, T., & Bolte, G. (2024). Identification of exposome clusters relevant for children's mental health: Results of the ABCD cohort study. Cooperation Conference of GMDS, DGSM, DGEpi, DGMS, and DGPH, Dresden, Germany.
21. Terzakis, M. E., Dohmen, M. E., Hornikx, C., et al. (2024). Characterization of façade sound insulation by impulse response measurements for various source position formats: A case study. In 53rd International Congress & Exposition on Noise Control Engineering (INTER-NOISE), Nantes, France.
22. Terzakis, M. E., Hornikx, M., van Hoorickx, C., et al. (2024). Spatial windowing for finite-size incident sound transmission coefficient of multi-component surfaces. In 53rd International Congress & Exposition on Noise Control Engineering (INTER-NOISE), Nantes, France.

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23. Terzakis, M. E., Hornikx, C., Naim, F., Fecht, D., Hansell, A. L., Gulliver, J. (2024). Estimation of low-frequency outdoor-to-indoor noise attenuation factors based on night-time noise exposure. 30th International Congress on Sound and Vibration, Amsterdam, The Netherlands.
24. van Kamp, Irene. (2024). Keynote – Noise and health in children (in a broader environmental context). Australian Acoustics Society ASS, Gold Coast, November 2024.
25. Wang, Zhiyang, et al. (2024, August). Relationships between the external exposome and proteome linked to mental health risk in adolescents. Oral presentation. 36th Annual ISEE Conference in Santiago, Chile.
26. Wang, Zhiyang. (2024, September). The relationship between the external environment and separation behavior among cotwins [Poster Presentation]. The Joint 7th World Congress on Twin Pregnancy and 19th Congress of the International Society of Twin Studies (ISTS), Assisi, Perugia, Italy, September 26th – 28th, 2024.
27. Wu, Fan, et al. (2024). Prenatal exposome and autism in children: An Equal-Life European multi-cohort study. ISEE Young Conference in Rennes, France (June 5–7, 2024). Abstracts ISEE Young 2024.

5 PhD Theses defended until 30.6.2025

1. Terzakis, M. E. (2025). *Outdoor-to-indoor sound propagation models for noise exposure studies*. [Dissertation (TU/e), Built Environment. Eindhoven University of Technology]. ISBN: 978-90-386-6281-7
2. Hulsman-Dohmen, M. E. (2025). *Children's Mental Health and the Environment: Examining the role of activity patterns and environmental noise exposure*. [Dissertation (TU/e), Built Environment. Eindhoven University of Technology]. ISBN: 978-90-386-6353-1 [PDF link](#)
3. Teeuwen, R. F. L. (2024). *Measuring children's access to urban greenspace*. [Dissertation (TU Delft), Delft University of Technology]. <https://doi.org/10.4233/uuid:b63f6779-cc98-40d0-9775-2af0054233e9>
4. Miliias, V. (2024). *Urban Co-accessibility*. [Dissertation (TU Delft), Delft University of Technology]. <https://doi.org/10.4233/uuid:0d2c77bc-5c20-4d1e-a02b-0c1de67ec728>
5. Loh, K. (2025). *Noise Exposure in Pre- and Primary Schools: Exploring Noise Effects on Young Children* [Dissertation, RWTH Aachen University]. <https://doi.org/10.18154/RWTH-2025-05615>
6. De Poortere, Nele. "Exploring the Effects of Noise Exposure: Insights from Young Adults and Children." PhD diss., Ghent University, 2024.

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7. Zhiyang Wang 'The effect of the environment on depression and underlying Genetic Influence in Adolescents and young adults (2025) University of Helsinki
<https://helda.helsinki.fi/server/api/core/bitstreams/920833eb-5330-4ef7-8e18-f85065f214df/content>

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